

GROWTH IN EXCHANGE TRADED FUNDS (ETFs), AWARENESS, ADVANTAGES AND INVESTMENT PATTERN – A STUDY W.R.T. URBAN BENGALURU

Lakshmi Priya M C, Assistant Professor ,SJB Institute of Technology , Research Scholar ,Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi : akshmpriya.gat@gmail.com

Dr. Ramanaiah G, Professor , Research Supervisor ,Acharya Institute of Technology–
ramanaiahg65@gmail.com

Abstract

Purpose: Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs) are one of the major source of finance to the industrialists and rising willing to participate in the investment avenue. Even small investor can invest on ETFs (Velu Murugan et al. 2015). When compare to other countries the Indian status of STF is not up to the expectation and has a long way to go in the ETFs market, but the numbers spell promising situation. As per SEBI report the ETFs has almost doubled from Rs. 1.54 lakh crores at the beginning of February 21 to Rs. 2.9 lakh crores by the end of February 21. ETFs are similar to mutual funds but unlike mutual funds, they are listed on an exchange and traded throughout the day (Abbas Vallok, 2022) ETFs are generally have lower expense rates and contain tax and vantage compared to traditional mutual funds and they allow investors to buy and sell shares at intraday market prices. ETFs have grown up tremendously as one of the successful and innovative product. The rational behind ETFs is that it requires small investment and gold required huge amount and it is impossible to small investors to invest in gold and hence they invest in the ETFs. Further, innovations in the area of financial service as responsible for the emergence of new product every now and then.

Approach: A precise capricious questionnaire was managed as schedule in order to avoid non-response, delay incompleteness and respecting covid norms. Respondents were approached in all four zonal areas. A total of 624 questionnaire were in the hand and out of 624 questionnaires only 600 were usable one forming success rate of 96.15%. Chi-square, contingency co-efficient, summation score, Kendall's co-efficient of concordance and factor analysis were performed to analyze and factor analysis were performed to analyze and present the data.

Findings: The study probed about the presence of significant variation in socio economic characteristics and found the existence of significant variation in the characteristics and also significant relationship between the two variables. The factor analysis highlights about existing types of investment. The factor, being most important like paper gold and NSS and this segment named as paper gold and NSS. The second factor explained about the respondents more awareness of safety, higher return and higher status. The third factor considered most important two factors, NBFC Deposit and commodities and these two are named as investors preference of NBFC and commodities. The major advantages being convenience and safety, affordability and opportunity to invest even by the small investors. All the drivers of investment pattern of investors reveals significance except appreciation and price stability, avoid committing mistakes, study systematic risk and study the available documents to verify the legitimacy of investment. All the factors <1500 are less significant and >1500 are more significant.

Keywords: Open ended, questionnaires, summation score, higher return, safety, mistakes, financial service, innovation.

Introduction

ETFs are attracting the investors attention as they are low cost and stock like features. These are safety way of investment and traded on stock exchange. ETFs another advantage is about tax advantage when compare to traditional mutual funds and they allow buy and sell shares at intraday prices. Over the years ETFs are attracting new investments. Innumerable investment options are available to the investors to park their investment. The parking of finance in an appropriate investment vehicle is driven by different factors. Investors are required to be rational and making rational study is required before investment. There are innumerable investment avenues that brings satisfactory returns with low risk

like pension plan. The choice of investment differ from one to another investor and factors that impress the investment behavior (Jain et al. 2012). The development of any economy is impressed by industrial and commerce activities. Researchers like Masoud (2013). Srinivasan (2012) opined that economic growth of a nation is directly linked to the stock market development. India, a developing economy needs developmental finance to develop infrastructures, requires huge capital. In order to be truly called India as ‘production hub’ requires huge amount of capital for infrastructure development. Stock market provides the necessary capital to take up industrial and commercial activities (Nazir et al. 2017). Individuals and industrial organizations invest in the stock market that forms capital which impacts to take up any industrial and thus funds outflow from individual households and organizations to the different areas of the economy. Investors prefer to invest on gold because of good return, liquidity, feature and wearing jewellery symbolizes status etc., But problems and draw backs like fear of loss by theft, loss by damages, loss of making charges and disadvantage of urgent need and selling. The small investors can not invest on gold and investment on gold requires huge investment. To make investment in gold possible for small investors there is an effective and popular type of investment called “Gold Exchange Trade Funds ETFs” (Mohd Saleem et al. 2013).

Statement of the problem

India as a developing economy has attracted the attention of global giants. In order to speed up infrastructural facilities and further embarking on economic development India needs huge size of capital requirements. Bengaluru is popularly nicknamed as ‘Science City’ ‘Silicon Valley’ ‘technology hub’ and in order to make ‘production hub’ requires sizeable amount of capital to invest in the development activities. Better investment environment should be created in addition to the need of rectifying certain cognitive and emotional weak which dominates the decision making of individuals. Investment decision also depends upon the type of investors, risk tolerance, capacity, education, occupation, age, sex, income, frequency of investment, living area etc., The small investors also impressed by demographic factors and they are impacted by needs, goals, objectives and demographic constraints while making investment decision. The investment behavior in real life is impacted by specific psychological factors like overconfidence, representativeness and herding behavior (Jain Ket al., 2015, Chiang et al., 2010). The investment trend is also impacted by quantum of dividend expectation, getting quick rich strategy, online trading, investors awareness programmes. The asset allocation strategy generally for investors depends upon low investors generally respond to be market movement (Al – Tamim, 2006). ETFs are becoming popular in India as they are like by small investors who sensitive to invest in gold because of problem of storing and theft. There is a growing trend among the Bengaluru investors towards ETFs and hence the financial experts should act swiftly to popularize the ETFs.

Growth in ETFs :

Source : Abbas Vantoli, (2022). Growth and development of Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs). *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 22(1), 1-7. <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/359511915>.

Fig-1 reveals that ETFs total assets have shown a continuous increase during the period 2016-2017. But the growth composition reveals a reverse trend from the year 2010-2017. Gold ETFs were predominant upto March 2015 but there after ETFs other than gold represented a major share in the total ETFs assets under management.

Table-1 : Growth of Assets of Gold and Non-gold ETFs

Year	Types of Schemes	AUM (Rs. Cr)	Percentage	No of Folios	Percentage
Mar-10	Gold ETF	1590.64	62.45%	147047	79.94%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	956.59	37.55%	36898	20.06%
	Total	2547.23	100.00%	183945	100.00%
Mar-11	Gold ETF	4400.2	63.62%	319679	75.61%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	2516.43	36.38%	103122	24.39%
	Total	6916.63	100.00%	422801	100.00%
Mar-12	Gold ETF	9886.06	86.02%	475314	76.20%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	1606.53	13.98%	148443	23.80%
	Total	11492.59	100.00%	623757	100.00%
Mar-13	Gold ETF	11647.82	88.75%	569169	76.95%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	1476.67	11.25%	170445	23.05%
	Total	13124.49	100.00%	739614	100.00%
Mar-14	Gold ETF	8676.32	65.71%	502613	71.31%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	4528.47	34.29%	202228	28.69%
	Total	13204.79	100.00%	704841	100.00%
Mar-15	Gold ETF	6654.87	45.23%	465765	66.56%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	8059.93	54.77%	233961	33.44%
	Total	14714.8	100.00%	699726	100.00%
Mar-16	Gold ETF	6345.55	28.32%	425914	61.05%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	16062.63	71.68%	271700	38.95%
	Total	22408.18	100.00%	697614	100.00%
Mar-17	Gold ETF	5479.81	10.98%	364110	39.79%
	ETF (Other than Gold)	44435.64	89.02%	551017	60.21%
	Total	49915.45	100.00%	915127	100.00%
CAGR	Gold ETF		19.33%		13.83%
	ETF (Other than Gold)		73.04%		47.14%
	Total		52.97%		25.76%

Source : Abbas Vattoli, (2022). Growth and development of Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs). *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 22(1), 1-7. <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/359511915>.

Table – 1 asserts the growth of Asset under management (AUM) of ETFs in India from the year 2010 to 2017. Table reveals that total AUM of ETFs has increased continuously from Rs. 2547.1 crores at the end of March 2010 to Rs. 49915.45 crores by the end of March 2017, with a compound annual growth rate of 52.97% for the period. During the same period Gold ETFs and ETFs other than gold have reported a CAGR of 19.33% and 73.04% respectively. Further, the table reveals that ETFs other than Gold has grown much faster than Gold ETFs. The number of folio in ETFs has grown from 183,945 at the end of March 2010 to 9,15,127 by the end of March 2017, with a compound annual growth rate 25.76% for a period of 7 years from 2010 to 2017.

Review of literature

Abbas Vattoli (2022) stated that ETFs are similar to mutual funds but unlike mutual funds, they are listed on an exchange and traded throughout the day, similar to stocks. They are generally lower expense rates and certain tax advantages compared to traditional mutual funds and permits the buyers and sellers to trade at intraday market prices. Further, the researcher expressed that ETFs are one of the most innovative and successful products introduced on exchanges and have grown tremendously. Nishmita Ahuja (2020) is of the opinion that investments are very keen in shaping wealth. Share market has a lot of ups and downs. The investors should be motivated to invest in mutual funds. The fear of loss should be eliminated in the mind of investors and for this the financial advisors, stock brokers and other expert must forward and organize various sessions for people who have less or no idea about how it works.

Aruna Polisetty et al., (2019) expressed that Indians are largely comfortable with traditional savings products over investing and within the investing universe, active fund management dominates passive. Product awareness is more significant to get more investors to ETFs so as to enhance liquidity and trading volume.

Sailaja Vedala (2018) found in their research that most of investors are still not aware of ETF funds and most of investors are still investing in mutual funds. The investment decision of investors depends mostly on age, risk taking capacity and the return for their investment and there is significant relationship between personal attributes and investors perception except in the case of educational qualification and knowledge.

Santhosh Kumar, G. et al., (2019) in their study conducted to examine the relationship between returns of physical gold and GTF reveals that standard deviation of the ICICI prudential Mutual Fund is high when compare to other ETFs, which reveals that there is high volatility of returns and the data is not normally distributed. The negative alpha states that the ETF did not perform well when compare to the benchmark of gold. Beta values reveals that systematic risk is negative for ICICI prudential Gold Exchange Traded Fund which leads to conclude that it has not performed well. Further, the researchers stated that the performance evaluation tools such as Shaper's Index, Treynor's Index, Sortino Ratio and Fara's Model Shows that ICICI Gold Exchange Traded Fund has performed better. The correlation analysis stated that physical gold and Gold ETFs have a strong relationship.

Objectives of the study

1. The study the socio-economic characteristics of respondents.
2. To analyse respondents awareness of paper gold investment.
3. To analyse the advantages of ETFs.
4. To study the investment pattern of investors.

Hypotheses

1. The socio-economic characteristics are not impacting on the study.
2. Respondents possess no awareness of paper gold investment.
3. Advantages of ETFs are lacking.
4. There is skewed investment pattern of investors.

Research questions

1. What are the reasons behind socio-economic characteristics not impressing on the study?
2. What is the level of respondents awareness on paper gold investment?
3. What are the advantages of ETFs?
4. What is the level of investment pattern of investors.

Research Methodology:

The present research work very much depends upon both primary and secondary data. Primary data collected through manageable questionnaire and secondary source include e-journals, books and internet. The research design nicknamed as 'blue print' 'pre projected activity' for the future aims at collecting data from samples to examine the demographic profile of respondents and to study their awareness towards ETFs, advantages and to examine investment pattern of respondents.

Zikmund defines (1988) research design as a 'master plan specifying the methods and procedure for collecting and analyzing the need information'. Research design is a strategy for answering the structured questionnaire using empirical data (Shona, 2021).

Participants: The participants in the study includes salaried employees 180, 100 retired persons, 90 business, 80 homemakers, 51 organizations, 43 industrialists, 28 each self employed and startup entrepreneurs.

Questionnaire design: A questionnaire which was structured and open ended was administered for the purpose of data collection from participants. Questions are logically arranged numbered properly. 3 point Likert Scale was performed to present the data and the remaining research hypotheses tested by performing chi-square, contingency co-efficient and factor analysis.

Universe of the study: The study is confined to Urban Bengaluru only.

Source of data: The study uses primary and secondary data. The primary data collected by administering questionnaire and secondary data include e-journals, books and internet.

Sampling technique: The sample for the study is based on the formula suggested by Bill Godden. When the universe exceeds 50,000, the formula used as follows. $Z^2 \times (P)(1-P) / C^2$. Where Z values

for confidence level are : 1.645 = 90% confidence level, 1.96 = 95% confidence level, 2.576 = 1.645 = 90% confidence level, 1.96 = 95% confidence level, 2.576 = 99% confidence level. Convenient sampling technique was performed.

Sample size = $3.8416 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 / 0.0016 = 600$

Bengaluru Urban was divided into four zones and from each zone 150 each respondents were approached. From each zone 150 respondents were approached. Further, the following information highlights area wise and sample covered.

Sl.No.	Zone	No. of areas covered	Sample
1	East	C. V. Ramannagar	50
		Domlur	50
		Pulakeshinagar	50
2	South	Viswesharapuram	50
		Jayanagar	50
		Basavanagudi	50
3	North	Dollar Colony	50
		HBR Layout	50
		Ganganagar	50
4	West	Hebbala	50
		Yashawanthapura	50
		Malleswaram	50

Method of analysis: The present work performed χ^2 , contingency co-efficient, summation score and factor analysis.

Data analysis and interpretation – Demographics – A

The socio-economic characteristics of respondents that are essential for the study includes gender, marital status, age, income, frequency of investment, occupation, savings created per month expected return etc. The significance of analyzing these characteristics assumes great importance as they are going to impress investment decisions.

Research question No. 1: What are the reasons behind demographics not impacting on the study?

Hypotheses No. 1: H₀: There exists no significant variation in the data.

Hypotheses No. 2: H₁: There exists significant variation in the data and all the demographics impress the study on paper gold investments.

Table – 2 asserts about the demographics of respondents. There are 480 males and 120 females, 405 married, 110 single and 85 divorcees, 220 respondents belongs to 28-42 years, 110 to the 33-37 years, 85 to the age group of 43-47 years and 80 to the group 28-32 years. The qualification data reveals that 190 are degree holders, 115 completed PUC 95 studied up to 10th standard, 90 are post graduates and 72 are professionals, 180 are salaried persons, 100 retired persons, 90 doing business, 80 are home makers, 51 are organizations, 43 industrialists, 28 are startup entrepreneurs. 180 respondents monthly income is 150 K – 170K, 110 each respondents monthly income falls in between 130K – 150K and >170K, 59 respondents income lies in between 110K – 130K, 41 respondents income is in between 70K – 90K and 40 respondents monthly income is in between 90K-110K. Monthly savings details reveals that 170 respondents save in between 8K – 10K, 120 in between 6K – 8K, 90 in between 10K-12K, 84 in between 4K – 6K. 510 respondents belongs to nuclear family and 90 joint family, 344 respondents possess residential building, 120 owns commercial building, 58 own sites. 336 respondents are regular monthly investors in ETFs, 194 not regular and 70 never, 408 are residing in developed area, 167 outskirts of Bengaluru and 25 reside in slum. 380 respondents preferred period of investment is long term 3 years, 170 medium term, 1 – 3 years and 50 short term – 1 year, 580 respondents are aware of ETFs, 280 preferred objective is safety, 140 returns, 120 low risk. The guiding factors are 324 authorized brokers, 126 newspapers, 78 friends and relatives and 72 self. The basis for select ETFs include 210 regular income, 135 safety 100 future prosperity. Out of 600 only 95 reinvested in physical gold and 460 said no and 215 preferred 30% regular annual income, 210 liked

35%, 90 like 25% annual return on ETFs. All the socio economic characteristics are significantly variable and reveals high degree of relationship between the characteristics and impact on the paper gold.

Research question No. 2: What is the level of respondents awareness on paper gold involvement?

Hypotheses No. 2: H₀: Respondents possess no awareness of paper gold investment?

H₁: There exist significant variation in the data and hence respondents possess awareness of paper gold investments.

Table – 3 to 7 reveals data about awareness level of existing types of investment. Table – 3 to 7 shows rotated materials that has the extracted factors by assigning a new none. All the factors having less than 0.5 are rejected from the analysis. The factor, is the most important factor like paper gold (0.91) and NSS (0.91). Hence this segment is named as paper gold and NSS.

The second kind of factors explained and research task the four important variable like Bank Deposits (0.95), P.O. Savings (0.81), mutual funds (0.95) and real estate (0.81).

The statements enabled that respondents are more aware of safety, higher return and high status. The third kind of factors the research took two important variables like NBFC Deposit (0.89) and commodities (0.89). These factors referred to as investors preferred of NBFC and commodities.

Research question No. 3: What are the advantages of ETFs?

Hypotheses No. 3, H₀: There exist no significant variation in the data.

H₁: There exist significant variation in the data and hence ETFs are advantageous to investors.

Table – 8 reveals data about advantages of ETFs. There are 324 respondents who stated strongly agree followed by 210 agreed, 75 somewhat agreed. Out of 324 respondents who said strongly agree, 53 stated about convenience and safety, 48 each stated about affordability and opportunity to invest even by the small investors, 37 said about assurance of purity. Out of 201 who reported agree, 43 expressed about convenience and safety, 29 spoke about affordability, 22 pointed at assurance of purity, 21 are of the opinion that opportunities to invest even by small investors. Out of 75 who said somewhat agree, 21 spoke about convenience and safety. 8 each reported about affordability and conversion. Further, 8 each spoke about easy to buy and sell and opportunity to invest even by small investors. 'w' fails to accept H₀ and concepts H₁ and hence it is concluded that there exist significant relationship between advantages and investment on paper gold.

Research question No. 4: What is the level of investment pattern of investor?

Hypotheses No. 4, H₀: There is a skewed investment pattern of investments.

H₁: There exists significant variation in the investment pattern of investors.

Table – 9 reveals data about awareness of investment pattern of investors. To measure the investment pattern of investors summation score technique was performed. It is arithmetically added numbers or quantification. Summation score was invented by Reses Likert (1932). To measure the level of investment pattern high point or low point is considered. All drivers shows satisfactory level except (1) appreciation and purchase price stability, (ii) avoid committing mistakes, (iii) study of systematic risk, & (iv) the stock of available documents.

Summary and discussion of findings:

The foremost objective of the present study is to know how far the socio economic factors impress the study on paper gold investments and to know the awareness of paper gold investment advantages of ETFs, types of ETFs preferred and investment pattern of investors deciding factors. In order to study systematically about ETFs experts judgments and their latest contributions also referred and considered in order to give the present work as most relevant. Survey technique is followed for the purpose of data collection. A well drafted, precise and capricious questionnaire was managed in the present study in order to collect the required information. Likert 3 point and summation score was adopted to present the multi opinions of participants. The target population identified in 12 areas of 4 zonal divisions of Bengaluru. The findings of the study were presented, analyzed and discussed by using chi-square contingency co-efficient, summation score, Kendall's co-efficient of concordance and factor analysis. Further the study found that factor being most important like paper gold and NSS and this segment was titled as paper gold and NSS. The second factor explained about the participants

awareness like safety, higher return and higher status. The third factor being significant considers two factors NBFC deposits and commodities and this segment was named as investors preference. The major advantages as per this study includes convenience and safety, affordability and opportunity to invest even by the small investors. All the drivers of investment pattern of investors reveals significant relationship except appreciation and price stability, avoid committing mistakes, study systematic risk and study the available documents. The summation reveals all factors are significant and more satisfactory since they are >1500 and the others which are below 1500 are less significant and satisfactory.

Based on the multi opinions expressed by 600 participants it was found that the Bengaluru participants are interested to invest in ETFs as they are least expense, easy to buy and sale and ETFs can also be traded in stock exchange. The advantages of ETFs are as per the opinions of participants reveals that convenience and safety, affordability and opportunity to invest even by the small investors and thus has been measured by Kendall's coefficient of concordance. The awareness of paper gold investment as revealed factor analysis includes paper gold and NSS in the first factor, the second factor reveals about most important variables such Bank deposits, post office savings, mutual funds, and real estate. The investment pattern of respondents was measured by summation score and it reveals high satisfaction except appreciation and price stability, avoid committing mistakes, study systematic risk and study the available documents.

Conclusion

The present study is an explorative in nature conducted to identify the demographic factors that influence the investors investment decision. Accurate information regarding the major factors that influence an individual investor has to be decided by different financial institutions and marketers in order to adjust pair marketing activities to achieve better results. Product awareness is significant to attract more and more investors to ETFs so as to enhance the liquidity and trading volume. ETFs by nature possess the advantages like hedge against inflation, open trading, easy transaction, tax benefits, inexpensive, secured and safe investment plant collateral. The study found about the presence of favorable socio-economic characteristics. First factor reveals about importance of paper gold and investment, second kind of factors reveals that bank deposits, PO Savings, mutual funds and real estate. The advantages include convenience and safety, affordability and opportunity to invest even by small investors and finally the investment pattern reveals all variables showing satisfactory except appreciation and purchase stability, avoid committing mistakes, study systematic data and the study of available data.

Table – 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents and satisfaction level of investments.

Characteristics	Chi-square	TV@0.05	df	result of x^2	'c'	Result of 'c'
Gender	216.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.51	High Degree
Marital status	316.75	5.991	2	Significant	0.58	High Degree
Age (in years)	303.61	12.592	6	Significant	0.57	High Degree
Qualification	130.78	11.070	5	Significant	0.42	High Degree
Occupation	238.90	14.067	7	Significant	0.53	High Degree
Monthly income (INR)	268.93	14.067	7	Significant	0.57	High Degree
Monthly savings (INR)	158.06	11.070	5	Significant	0.46	High Degree

Type of family	294.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.57	High Degree
Type of assets possessing	561.91	9.488	4	Significant	0.69	High Degree
Frequency of investment in ETFs	177.16	5.991	2	Significant	0.48	High Degree
Place of residence	374.89	5.991	2	Significant	0.62	High Degree
Preferred period of investment	179.00	5.991	2	Significant	0.48	High Degree
Awareness of ETFs	522.66	3.841	1	Significant	0.68	High Degree
Objective behind investment	173.33	7.815	3	Significant	0.47	High Degree
Financial advisors	308.28	5.991	2	Significant	0.58	High Degree
Guiding factors of investment	280.80	5.991	2	Significant	0.56	High Degree
Basis for selection of ETFs	107.91	9.488	4	Significant	0.39	High Degree
Reinvestment in physical gold	170.66	3.841	1	Significant	0.56	High Degree
Expected return on ETFs	185.41	11.070	4	Significant	0.48	High Degree

Field Survey

Table - 2: KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.587
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	805.472
	df	15
	Sig.	.001

Awareness of existing types of investment

Table – 3: Communalities

Type of investment	Initial	Extraction
Paper Gold	1.00	1.00
Gold and silver	1.00	0.99
Bank Deposits	1.00	0.93
Post office savings	1.00	0.88
NBFC Deposited	1.00	0.95
Public Provident Fund	1.00	0.59
NSC	1.00	0.38
NSS	1.00	1.00
Life Insurance	1.00	0.99
Mutual Funds	1.00	0.93
Real Estate	1.00	0.88
Commodities	1.00	0.95
Shares and stocks	1.00	0.59

Fixed income securities	1.00	0.38
-------------------------	------	------

Table 4: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.50	39.25	39.25	5.50	39.25	39.25	2.05	14.65	14.65
2	2.47	17.66	56.91	2.47	17.66	56.91	3.27	23.33	37.97
3	2.08	14.87	71.78	2.08	14.87	71.78	2.28	16.27	54.24
4	1.77	12.64	84.42	1.77	12.64	84.42	1.91	13.65	67.90
5	1.08	7.70	92.13	1.08	7.70	92.13	1.92	13.71	81.60
6	0.61	4.35	96.47						
7	0.49	3.53	100.00						
8	0.00	0.00	100.00						
9	0.00	0.00	100.00						
10	0.00	0.00	100.00						
11	0.00	0.00	100.00						
12	0.00	0.00	100.00						
13	0.00	0.00	100.00						
14	0.00	0.00	100.00						

Table – 5: Component Matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Paper Gold	0.74	-0.46	0.26	-0.38	0.15
Gold and silver	0.79	-0.55	0.21	0.38	0.26
Bank Deposits	0.61	0.65	0.32	0.04	-0.18
Post office savings	0.73	0.53	-0.16	-0.09	-0.18
NBFC Deposit	0.79	-0.14	-0.55	0.02	0.08
Public Provident Fund	0.20	-0.33	0.00	0.05	-0.66
NSC	-0.01	0.30	-0.03	-0.03	0.54
NSS	0.74	-0.46	0.26	-0.38	0.15
Life insurance	0.79	-0.33	0.21	0.38	0.26
Mutual Funds	0.61	0.65	0.32	0.04	-0.18
Real Estate	0.73	0.53	-0.16	-0.09	-0.18
Commodities	0.79	-0.14	-0.55	0.02	0.08
Shares and stocks	0.20	0.33	0.00	0.05	-0.66
Fixed Income Securities	-0.01	0.36	-0.03	-0.03	0.54

Table – 6: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Paper Gold	0.91	0.10	0.22	0.32	0.11
Gold and silver	0.36	0.16	0.27	0.87	0.02
Bank Deposits	0.06	0.95	-0.02	0.16	-0.03
Post office savings	0.09	0.81	0.46	0.01	0.00
NBFC Deposit	0.26	0.13	0.89	0.26	0.05
Public Provident Fund	0.07	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.75
NSC	-0.02	0.06	0.03	0.02	-0.61
NSS	0.91	0.10	0.22	0.32	0.11

Life insurance	0.36	0.16	0.27	0.87	0.02
Mutual Funds	0.06	0.95	-0.02	0.016	-0.03
Real Estate	0.09	0.81	0.46	0.01	0.00
Commodities	0.23	0.18	0.89	0.26	0.05
Shares and stocks	0.07	0.85	0.09	0.05	0.75

Table - 7: Advantages of ETFs

Advantages	SA	A	SWA	RT	RT ²
Transparency in pricing	31	18	5	54	2916
Tax Efficiency	24	17	5	46	2116
Affordability	48	29	8	85	7225
Assurance of purity	37	22	6	65	4225
Convenience and safety	53	43	21	117	13689
Emerging strong asset	30	18	6	54	2916
Conversion	28	15	8	51	2601
Early purchased and sold	25	18	8	51	2601
Opportunity to invest even by small investors	48	21	8	77	5929
Total	324	201	75	600	44218

Source: Field Survey

Table - 8: Awareness of Investment Pattern of Investors

Drivers of investment pattern	SA	A	SWA	Score
Income stability – regulation of income @ a consistent rate is necessary	505	60	35	
	1515	120	35	1670
Appreciation and purchase price stability – purchase at right time leads to appreciation	300	260	40	
	900	520	40	1460
Liquidity and freedom from all investments – law relating to minds, states, trust, shares and insurance should be studied	370	180	50	
	1110	360	50	1520
Investment on tangible and intangible, a separate study is required – many times lost because of inflation and social collapse	442	130	28	
	1326	260	28	1614
Should be successful in achieving better rate of return and in excess should be earned	437	125	38	
	1311	250	38	1599
Requires superior analytical skill	506	59	35	
	1518	118	35	1671
Balance profit potential and risk factors	385	167	48	
	1155	334	48	1537
Avoid committing mistakes – help the investor to keep away from letting excitement make him more too quickly	330	231	39	
	990	462	39	1491
Overcome while dealing with stock the physical difficulty, intellectual difficulty and psychological difficulty	390	166	44	
	1170	332	44	1546
Invest in different products institutional players (Mutual Funds, Corporate bodies, foreign institutions, gold & ETFs)	365	200	35	
	1095	400	35	1530
Risk bearing capacity should not be impacted by personal, economical, environment, situational factors, family factors etc.,	398	164	38	
	1194	328	38	1560
Avoiding wrong decisions wrong timing of investments, nature of investment, corporate shares or brands, chit funds, benefit funds are highly risky as they are unorganised.	389	183	28	
	1167	366	28	1561
	300	159	41	

Study systematic risks – external uncontrollable and natural industrial unsystematic arises out of controllable factors management failure, labour strike, raw material shortage	900	318	41	1259
Investment pattern of investors on different products varies due to increase in the cost of production, wage rise, lower maturity and business risk	425	130	45	
	1275	260	45	1580
While investing on bullion, industry gold silver, metals the investor should follow watch and wait policy.	506	56	38	
	1518	152	38	1658
Investors should understand investment products v/s stock or fixed income	423	149	28	
	1269	298	28	1595
Ascertain easy trading financial assets – buying about implies liability of issuing concern and asset to the investor	430	118	52	
	1290	236	52	1578
A stable currency, a well-organized monetary system are necessary and prerequisite to an investment market	510	54	36	
	1530	108	36	1676
Choice of investment whether ETFs / gold / stock / commodities etc.,	520	65	15	
	1560	130	15	1705
Determine the economic climate whether conducive and capable of encouraging the growth of business sector especially capital market	432	138	28	
	1302	276	28	1606
Across study of performance of different products	401	148	51	
	1203	296	51	1550
Study the available documents to verify the legitimacy of investment	345	167	88	
	1035	334	88	1457

References

- Abbas Vattoli, (2022). Growth and development of Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs). **Global Journal of Management and Business Research**, 22(1), 1-7. <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/359511915>.
- Aruna Polisetty., & Vijaya Kittu Mandya. (2019). Growth and development of ETFs in India. **Internal Journal of Advance and Innovative Research**, 1(x1), 90-94.
- Jain, R., Jain C., & Jain, C. (2015). Behavioural biases in the decision making of individual investors. **I&P Journal of Management Research**, 14: 7-27.
- Masoud, N.M.H. (2013). The impact of stock market performance upon economic growth. **International journal of economics and financial issue**, 3(4), 784-798.
- Nazir, M.S., Nawaz, M.N., & Gilani. (2017). Relationship between economic growth and stock market development relationship between economic growth & stock market development. **African journal of business management**, 4(16), 3473-3479.
- Sailaja Vedala. (2018). A study on understanding the relationship between personal attributes and investor perception towards ETF Funds investment. **Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical & Control System**, 10(8), Special Issue, 204-209.
- Sailaja, V.N. (2018). A study on understanding the relationship between personal attributes and investors perception towards ETFs investment. **Journal of Advanced research in Dynamics and Control systems**. 10(8), Special issue 204-209.
- Sathish Kumar, B., & Ram Raj., G. (2019). **Gold Vs Gold Exchange Traded Funds, An empirical study in India Economic Affairs**, 64(4), 703-710.
- Srinivasan, P. (2012). Determinants of equity share prices in India: A panel data approach, **The Romanian Economic Journal**, 46(6), 205-228.
- Velumurugan G., Selvan., & Abdul Nazir, N. (2013). An empirical analysis on perception of investors towards various investment avenues. **Mediterranean Journal of Social Science**, 6(4), 427-435.